

SAMBAFEST DANCERCISE VIDEO AND LEARNERS' PERFORMANCE IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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SambaFest Dancercise Video and Learners' Performance in Physical Education

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Abstract

The SambaFest Dancercise video was developed as a Teaching Guide for dance instruction, with a specific duration of 1 hour allocated for its implementation in class. The study employed a Descriptive-evaluative research design to determine and evaluate the effectiveness of the SambaFest Dancercise video. A Quasi-experimental research design was utilized to analyze the impact of the video on the dance performances of Grade Nine students in their Physical Education (P.E) course. The experimental group received instruction using the SambaFest Dancercise video, while the control group received 1 hour of traditional dance instruction. Random sampling was used to select participants, and the validation instrument assessed the video's content, relevance, acceptability, and instructional aspects. The SambaFest Dancercise video was evaluated as meeting above-standard criteria in these dimensions by a panel of evaluators. Result indicated that students in the experimental group demonstrated significantly higher dance performance in the post-test compared to their pre-test scores. Furthermore, significant differences were observed between the pre-test results of the control and experimental groups, with the experimental group showing greater improvement. Additionally, the mean gain in post-test results was significantly higher in the experimental group compared to the control group.

Keywords: *SambaFest dancercise video, innovative strategy, dance performance*

Introduction

The pandemic brought on by COVID-19 is one of the factors contributing to the deterioration in learners' performance in physical education. Due to the ban on in-person instruction, teaching dance nowadays is difficult. PE teachers faced many difficulties because of the shift to modular, online learning and other ways that was sparked by the pandemic. Teachers in physical education (PE), a historically undervalued topic, relied on "trial-and-error" techniques because they had little to no training or experience with remote PE instruction. The COVID-19 pandemic has stopped this fast-paced civilization in its tracks.

The pandemic's effects are devastating, and the only way to stop the disease's rapid spread is through social division. Many elements of people's lives, including their daily exercise routines, have been hampered by the lockdown that has been imposed. This has caused several psychological issues as well as significant fitness and health issues. Additionally, it has led to the closing of shops, public areas, activity centers, and other venues where people congregate in general (Kaur et al., 2020).

However, based on the P.E. grades of Grade 9 during the previous three years, learners performed very poorly in dancing and other physical activities even before the pandemic. Since there are frequently no dance seminars or trainings for P.E teachers, they frequently lack the knowledge necessary to instruct various dances.

In the Department of Education, one of the hardest lessons to introduce to students is the recreational activities like dances and exercises (MPS, 2018) because students are more inclined with new high technologies using their cellphones and other gadgets and they are bored on the steps taught by their Physical Education (P.E.) teachers.

The greatest way to prevent student boredom was to provide the K–12 Curriculum (2015) to Filipino learners through Teacher's Guides (TGs) and Curriculum Guides (CGs) that contained the appropriate competencies to be learned by the students in the teaching–learning process in the classroom. Dances are a part of the Physical Education (P.E.) topic and are covered in the exercises and leisure activities that make up the competency. The curriculum guides for Grade Nine (9) will reveal it.

The interactive application SambaFest Dancercise was created to teach dance as a form of exercise in their Physical Education theme. They use improvised maracas and give an outline of the samba dance and festival dance remix. The basic samba and Timpuyog festival dance routines from the Lambayong municipality in Sultan Kudarat are given a particular twist in this dance. A PowerPoint presentation with video of a group of people dancing and the teaching guide for teaching dance as a form of exercise will be shown via Zoom Meeting or Google Meet. This dance has a purpose that tells us a lot about the culture it symbolizes.

The researcher found the best remedy to integrate something unique to the dance to be taught to the learners. It's an inventive mashup of basic samba movements and basic figures from Lambayong's Timpuyog festival dance, with a twist of improvised maracas to keep them entertained during the dance competition. The researcher's goal is to provide the dance tutorial in a PowerPoint presentation and on a CD tape or USB with the best model and dancers possible. The researcher's major goal is to see if this teaching guide is beneficial in improving their dancing performance and contributing to an increase in their academic grades in Physical Education.

Research Questions

Generally, the study investigated the effect of SambaFest Dancercise Video on the Learner's Performance in Physical Education.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of the quality of SambaFest dance video in terms of:
 - 1.1. content;
 - 1.2. relevance;
 - 1.3. acceptability; and
 - 1.4. instructional aspect?
2. What is the level of the learners' dance performance in control and experimental groups in the pre-test and post-test results in terms of:
 - 2.1. timing;
 - 2.2. mastery;
 - 2.3. enthusiasm;
 - 2.4. participation; and
 - 2.5. creativity in choreography?
3. Is there a significant difference in the pre-test results between the control and experimental groups?
4. Is there a significant difference in the post-test results between the control and experimental groups?
5. Is there a significant difference in the mean gain test results between the control and experimental groups?

Literature Review

Samba

Brazilian music and dancing are known as samba. Samba has antebellum and antebellum slave roots. According to legend, the word "samba" is derived from the West African word semba, which denotes a physical invitation or navel thrust and is connected to religious and community ceremonies in Africa. In the 16th century, Portuguese traders brought slaves from West Africa to Brazil's Bahia province (Przybylek, 2019).

It is a dance that is performed with a partner on the dance floor. The samba distinguishes out ballroom dance genres, which generally depart from their roots. According to Elite Dance Studio, ballroom samba evolved through time because of the blending of traditional samba and maxixe (a tango-inspired dance) (2019).

Dance

Dance is another emerging complementary therapy that offers social, psychological, and physical advantages. In response to musical cues and changes in direction, dance workouts demand continual weight transfer between the legs at various temperatures. When people with Parkinson's disease take dancing courses, their motor abilities, quality of life, social skills, and drive to retain their body movement patterns all improve (dos Santos et al., 2020).

Dance in Physical Education

In many countries, dance has long been covered in physical education (PE) classes. Despite this, research reveals that dance is underutilized and undervalued in physical education. Three main areas of dance knowledge are covered in the literature: "dancing as cultural preserver," "dancing as bodily action," and "dancing as expression" (Engdahl et al., 2021).

Dance in the Philippines

The customs and culture of the Philippines are well-known. During the colorful celebrations, it is possible to see costumes, music, and dances. Filipino culture, customs, way of life, and traditional and folk dances are displayed. The Philippines' folk dances are as varied as the history of the nation, although modern audiences rarely witness them (Hofilena, 2019).

Garcia (2020) asserts that by using dance literature, physical education teachers were able to instruct these ASEAN ethnic dances in a genuine way. In a similar vein, there are four (4) emerging criteria that cover various constructs/concepts in teaching and presenting ASEAN folk dances: authenticity, which includes step interpretation based on literature, the dance's history, musicality, cultural, and religious aspects; performance, which includes proper execution, dance artistry, and coordination; choreography, which includes staging and floor patterns; and visual impact, which includes costumes, props, and other visual elements. Finally, teachers of physical education need to be educated and skilled in teaching ASEAN ethnic dances.

Performance-based Learning

There are learning standards for every discipline that set academic objectives and specify what qualifies as proficiency in achieving those goals. When possible, performance-based exercises should combine two or more academic fields while also addressing the demands of the twenty-first century, including those for creativity and invention, critical thinking and problem solving, and teamwork and collaboration. For the Information Literacy and Media Literacy standards, performance-based learning is also necessary (Ralph et al., 2020).

Reasons to Dance

While it would be impossible to list them all, the following are some of the more significant advantages of dancing. Laughter and fun—dancing can provide a lot of entertainment; Dancing is a kind of exercise. Dancers gain inspiration and motivation as they become lost in the dance, and Dancing allows professional dancers to build connections (Budden, 2019).

In their concerts, vocalists occasionally dance, according to Budden (2019). Until someone in the audience gives particular attention, a dancer can only be acknowledged in a limited circle. A dancer may go from "unknown" to "star" relatively immediately. Adding dance to a performance can't help but improve it, and the audience can't help but pay attention. Dance attracts people with a diverse range of tastes, emotions, needs, and backgrounds because of its diversity. As a result, dancing has developed into both an art form and a language that is understood by all people.

Basic Education Competency in K-12 in the Philippine

Lack of readiness for the workforce, entrepreneurship, or higher education among high school graduates was a result of this low educational quality (Almerino et al., 2020). Furthermore, high school graduates lack the emotional maturity required for success in the workplace. As a result, the new plan will contain culture, history, and reality-based teachings, activities, music, poems, chronicles, and films. Thoughts on catastrophe avoidance, climate change, and information and communication technology (ICT) are also included. They want students to gain in-depth information, accomplishments, beliefs, and attitudes by maintaining continuity and consistency throughout grades (Almerino et al., 2020).

The Senior High School program was extended by two years under the K12 Basic Education Program, or Republic Act 10533, which superseded the previous curriculum. The new curriculum placed an emphasis on the advancement of critical thinking and scientific abilities to support the nation's economic and social development in the twenty-first century.

The new courses are meant to give students the knowledge and abilities they need to find employment or continue their education after high school. Beginning at age five, basic education transitions from informal to formal instruction in classes one through twelve (Tupas et al., 2020).

Video Instructional Materials

Finding strategies to magnify their curriculum might be challenging for new teachers. For learners to develop a deeper comprehension of the material, video snippets can be a very helpful tool. It's critical to be conscientious of how frequently and extensively we use video, and it's crucial to have a specific reason for doing so (Alber, 2019).

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive-evaluative research design to determine and evaluate the effectiveness of the SambaFest Dancercise Video as a teaching tool for Grade 9 students at Kapingkong National High School. The evaluation focused on assessing the quality of the video in Physical Education, considering its content, relevance, acceptability, instructional, and technical aspects. The study utilized a quasi-experimental research design, specifically employing pre-test and post-test assessments to examine the impact of the SambaFest Dancercise video on the dance performance of Grade Nine learners.

Participants

Participants included sixty Grade Nine students from Kapingkong National High School, selected through random sampling during the school year 2020-2021. The study also involved a panel of twenty evaluators comprising teachers with dance backgrounds, dance choreographers, trainers, Master of Arts in Teaching Physical Education graduates, Physical Education teachers, IT experts, and Zumba instructors.

Instruments

Data collection instruments included a validation tool and a treatment instrument utilizing the SambaFest Dancercise Video. Additionally, a test instrument assessed the video's content, relevance, acceptability, and instructional aspects.

The SambaFest Dancercise Video, designed as an interactive teaching guide for dance exercises in Physical Education, incorporates samba dance and Timpuyog festival dance elements, enhanced with improvised maracas. The video is available online via CD or USB and is presented using PowerPoint in virtual classes through platforms like Zoom Meeting or Google Meet.

The evaluation instrument was being answered by the panel of evaluators which was composed of Five (5) teachers with background in dancing, Five (3) Dance Choreographer, two (2) Dance trainers, two (2) Master of Arts in Teaching Physical Education Graduate teachers, four (4) Physical Education (P.E) teachers, two (2) IT expert, and two (2) Zumba Instructor. They evaluated the said teaching guide in the extent of its acceptability in terms of content, relevance, acceptability, and instructional aspects.

To determine the improvement level of the learner's dance performance, the rules and guidelines with relevant rubrics that serve as a

criterion in judging their dance performance was being utilized with the following indicators with different criteria like Timing, mastery, enthusiasm, participation, and creativity in choreography.

Procedure

Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the Dean of the Graduate School, SKSU, Tacurong City. Additional approvals were sought from the Schools Division Superintendent of Sultan Kudarat and the principal of Kapingkong National High School.

In the experimental group, the SambaFest Dancercise Video was integrated into virtual classes over a one-week period, with students rehearsing and performing the dance exercises repeatedly. The duration of instruction with the video amounted to one hour per session, totaling one week. The control group received modular instruction on samba and festival dances, completing activities independently and submitting recorded performances for assessment.

Pre-test assessments using dance rubrics established baseline performance levels for both groups. Follow-up assessments were conducted via video submissions to evaluate learner performance, with arrangements made for potential face-to-face evaluations if permitted. A dance showdown was organized for both groups, judged by teachers and a panel of experts using standardized rubrics.

Ethical Considerations

It's critical that studies adhere to ethical guidelines. Fundamentally, this shaped the study's actual goals, which were knowledge, accuracy, and error avoidance, and it promoted ideals necessary for cooperative work, such justice, accountability, mutual respect, and trust. This study adhered to and respected the research ethics guidelines found in the Belmont Report (2010) to assure ethical research. These values honor an individual's autonomy, beneficence and non-maleficence, fairness, informed consent, honesty, confidentiality, and conflict of interest.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered relevant to the study, specifically on the development and evaluation of the SambaFest Dancercise video and the learner's performance in their physical education.

The Extent of the Quality of SambaFest Dancercise in terms of Content, Relevance, Acceptability, and Instructional Aspects.

Table 1-8 show the level of the extent of the quality of SambaFest Dancercise video in terms of content, relevance, acceptability and instructional aspects. The level of performance and the significant difference of learner's performance.

The Extent of the Quality of SambaFest Dancercise Video in terms of Content

Table 1 focused on the extent of the quality of sambafest dancercise in terms of content.

Table 1. *The Mean Extent of the Quality of SambaFest Dancercise Video in terms of Content*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. The SambaFest Dancercise video aligns with K-12 Curriculum goals.	4.80	0.41	Outstanding
2. The learning objectives of the video are stated stated.	4.60	0.50	Outstanding
3. The sequence of activities is appropriate to the learners.	4.45	0.51	Very Satisfactory
4. The directions are specific and understandable.	4.55	0.60	Outstanding
5. The exercises are sufficient for practice sessions.	4.55	0.60	Outstanding
6. The SambaFest Dancercise video are easy to follow and understand.	4.30	0.66	Very Satisfactory
7. The SambaFest Dancercise video. contains interesting steps for learners.	4.50	0.51	Outstanding
8. The SambaFest Dancercise video is localized.	4.65	0.59	Outstanding
9. The SambaFest Dancercise allows individualized and experiential learning.	4.75	0.44	Outstanding
10. The content provides a drive for further enhancement.	4.55	0.51	Outstanding
Overall	4.57	0.28	Outstanding

Table 1 presents the mean extent of the quality of Sambafest Dancercise video in terms of content that the SambaFest Dancercise aligns with K-12 Curriculum goals got the highest mean of 4.80 which is excellent wherein The SambaFest Dancercise video are easy to follow and understand. Got the lowest mean of 4.30 which means very satisfactory. The indicators acquired a grand mean of 4.57 which is Outstanding and meets 81% and above quality of standard.

The conclusions show that each field has learning standards that establish academic expectations and specify what constitutes proficiency in satisfying those levels. Performance-based exercises should, whenever possible, fulfill the demands of the twenty-first century and integrate two or more topics (Kelly, 2019).

The Extent of the Quality of SambaFest Dancercise Video in terms of Relevance

Table 2 focuses on the extent of the quality of sambafest dancercise in terms of relevance.

The table above shows the extent of the quality of SambaFest Dancercise video in terms of relevance. The SambaFest Dancercise video instructional materials are suitable for individual use has the highest mean of 4.75 which means outstanding while The content

provides an impetus for further research got the lowest rating of 4.40 which means very satisfactory. The provision of table 2 garnered the overall mean rating of 4.60 with its descriptive rating of outstanding and implies satisfying 81% and above quality of standard.

Table 2. *Mean Extent of the Quality of SambaFest Dancercise Video in terms of Relevance*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. SambaFest Dancercise video activities are appropriate and relevant to students' needs.	4.65	0.49	Outstanding
2. The SambaFest Dancercise video provides evidence of effectiveness through pre-test and post-test results.	4.50	0.51	Outstanding
3. The content provides an impetus for further research.	4.40	0.50	Very Satisfactory
4. The exercises are based on the knowledge and abilities that are anticipated to be honed by aspiring dancers.	4.65	0.49	Outstanding
5. The SambaFest Dancercise video meets the minimum requirements set for the P.E subject	4.50	0.51	Outstanding
6. The SambaFest Dancercise video instructional materials are suitable for individual use.	4.75	0.44	Outstanding
7. The instructional video gives the teacher, dance instructors, and promising dancers an opportunity for the desired skills in dancing.	4.55	0.51	Outstanding
8. The SambaFest Dancercise video topics are attuned to the interest and urgent needs.	4.60	0.50	Outstanding
9. The SambaFest Dancercise video could develop mastery of dance concepts.	4.70	0.47	Outstanding
10. The SambaFest Dancercise video package is appropriate for teaching dance to learners.	4.65	0.49	Outstanding
Overall	4.60	0.23	Outstanding

The fact that there are various styles of samba music and that the samba rhythm continues to be a highly popular foundation for non-Brazilian creators of samba music means that learners may easily perform the steps and actions that go along with the music.

The Extent of the Quality of SambaFest Dancercise Video in terms of Acceptability.

Table 3 focuses on the extent of the quality of sambafest dancercise in terms of acceptability.

Table 3. *Mean Extent of the Quality of SambaFest Dancercise Video in terms of Acceptability*

<i>Acceptability</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. The SambaFest Dancercise video achieves the purpose for which it is intended to.	4.70	0.47	Outstanding
2. The SambaFest Dancercise video can be used to motivate the promising dancers in learning dance concepts.	4.50	0.51	Outstanding
3. The instructional materials are applicable to real –life situations of the promising dancers.	4.65	0.59	Outstanding
4. The SambaFest Dancercise video provides students with dance steps which develop their dancing skills.	4.35	0.59	Very Satisfactory
5. The video plays smoothly and is not damaged.	4.40	0.68	Very Satisfactory
6. The strategies and instructional materials fit the target audience.	4.50	0.51	Outstanding
7. The SambaFest Dancercise video is culturally and ethically sensitive, free of bias and reflects diverse audience.	4.40	0.60	Very Satisfactory
8. The SambaFest Dancercise video caters the learning needs of the promising dancers.	4.45	0.51	Very Satisfactory
9. The SambaFest Dancercise video meets the minimum standard.	4.55	0.51	Outstanding
10. The SambaFest Dancercise video package is valuable and could be promoted to others.	4.45	0.51	Very Satisfactory
Overall	4.50	0.33	Outstanding

Table 3 shows that the SambaFest dancercise video achieves the purpose for which it is intended to have the highest mean of 4.70 which means outstanding while The SambaFest Dancercise video provides students with dance steps which develop their dancing skills with a mean of 4.35 which means very satisfactory. It has an overall mean of 4.50 with its descriptive rating of outstanding. It implies that SambaFest Dancercise video in terms of acceptability meets 81% and above quality of standard.

Based on the findings, performance-based learning is successful when students engage in completing relevant and engaging tasks or activities. This is demonstrated by using the SambaFest Dancercise video. This type of instruction is designed to aid students in learning and applying concepts, honing skills, and forming independent and teamwork work habits. One that enables a student to show proof of comprehension through a transfer of abilities is the concluding activity or outcome for performance-based learning (Kelly, 2019).

Extent of the Quality of SambaFest Dancercise video in terms of Instructional Aspect

Table 4 focuses on the extent of the quality of SambaFest Dancercise video in terms of instructional aspect.

Table 4 above reveals the extent of the quality of SambaFest Dancercise video in terms of instructional aspect. There are two indicators

got the highest mean of 4.70 which means outstanding, and this is the The SambaFest Dancercise video contains easily understandable direction for users and SambaFest Dancercise video facilitates easy integration into the dance. The indicators got the lowest mean of 4.45 which means very satisfactory is the The SambaFest Dancercise video instructions has no errors, contains the video stimulates promising dancers` interest and curiosity.

Table 4. *The Mean Extent of the Quality of SambaFest Dancercise video in terms of Instructional Aspect*

<i>Instructional Aspect</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. The SambaFest Dancercise video contains easily understandable direction for users.	4.70	0.47	Outstanding
2. The SambaFest Dancercise video instructions has no errors.	4.45	0.51	Very Satisfactory
3. The SambaFest Dancercise video contains basic dance exercises for active learning.	4.45	0.51	Very Satisfactory
4. The SambaFest Dancercise video is interactive.	4.55	0.60	Outstanding
5. The SambaFest Dancercise video as teaching guide techniques are appropriate.	4.55	0.51	Outstanding
6. The SambaFest Dancercise video stimulates promising dancers` interest and curiosity.	4.45	0.51	Very Satisfactory
7. The SambaFest Dancercise video shows strong relevance to promising dancers` experiences.	4.60	0.50	Outstanding
8. The SambaFest Dancercise video is a useful instructional tool.	4.65	0.49	Outstanding
9. The SambaFest Dancercise video facilitates easy integration to other dances.	4.70	0.47	Outstanding
10. The SambaFest Dancercise video concepts have been simplified.	4.65	0.49	Outstanding
Overall	4.58	0.29	Outstanding

The SambaFest Dancercise video in terms of instructional aspect has an overall mean of 4.50 with a descriptive rating of outstanding that meets 81% and above quality of standard.

The Basic Education Competency in K–12 in The Philippines (2012) statement, which states that students understand their lessons well if they can relate to them, supports the findings. The new plan in every teaching presentation will include lessons, activities, songs, poems, chronicles, and videos based on culture, history, and reality and with Information and Communication Technology or ICT. They want the students to acquire in-depth knowledge, accomplishments, values, and attitudes through continuity and consistency throughout every school level thanks to relevance.

The Mean Level of the Dance Performance of the Learners in the Control Group and Experimental Group in the Pre-test and Post-Test Results

Table 5 presents the mean level of the dance performance of the learners in the control group and experimental group in the pre-test and post-test results.

Table 5. *The Mean Level of the Dance Performance of the Learners in the Control Group and Experimental Group in the Pre-test and Post-Test Results*

<i>Group</i>	<i>Control</i>		<i>Experimental</i>	
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
Pre-test	3.20	0.50	3.27	0.36
Post-test	3.64	0.20	4.43	0.12
Mean gain	0.45	0.37	1.16	0.35

The table above presents the mean level of the dance performance of the learners that in the control group, the pre-test got the mean of 3.20 while the post-test got the mean of 3.64 with a mean gain score of 0.45. In the experimental group, the pre-test got the mean of 3.27 while the post-test got the mean of 4.43 with a mean gain score of 1.16. It means that learner`s dance performance in the post-test is higher than the pre-test. The results supported by the statement of Cepni (2005), show that our time is technology time. He stated that the computers and instructional materials being used as both tool and method are effective for students on increasing the concentration on the course, understanding lesson, synthesizing, and improving positive thoughts for the course.

The Significant Difference in the Pre-test Results between the Control and Experimental Groups

The table below reveals the T-test analysis of the pre-test between the control and experimental groups

Table 6. *The T-test Analysis of the Pre-test Results between the Control and Experimental Groups*

<i>Group</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean Diff</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>PValue</i>	<i>interpretation</i>
Control	30	3.20	0.50	0.07	58	0.6	0.55	Not significant
Experimental	30	3.27	0.36					

The table reveals the significant difference in the pre-test results between the control and experimental groups. Since $t(58)=0.6$, $p=0.55$, and p -value did not meet the set level of confidence at .05, I conclude that there is no significant difference in the pre-test results between the control group ($M=3.20, SD=0.50$) and experimental group ($M=3.27, SD=0.36$). The result implies that the mean pre-test

results are comparable.

It signifies that during the conduct of the pre-test, students have no idea on what they are doing just like the mind of a human at birth. This statement was supported by John Locke's philosophy, that the human mind is a tabula rasa which is a blank slate without rules for processing data, and that data is added and rules for processing are formed solely by one's sensory experiences.

The Significant Difference of the Post-test Results between the Control and Experimental Groups

The table below reveals the significant difference of the post-test between the control and experimental groups.

Table 7. *The T-test Analysis of the Post-Test Results between the Control Group and Experimental Group*

Group	N	Mean	SD	Mean diff	df	t	Pvalue	Interpretation
Control	30	3.64	0.20					
Experimental	30	4.43	0.12	0.78	58	18.03	<0.00001	Significant

Since $t(58)=18.03$, $p<0.00001$, and pvalue is less than the set level of confidence at .05, I conclude that there is a significant difference in the post test results between the control group ($M=3.64, SD=0.20$) and experimental group ($M=4.43, SD=0.12$). The result of the experimental group is significantly higher than the control group. This means that there is a significant difference between the two means.

The result implies that in the post-test, there is a significant difference between the control and experimental groups in terms of learner's performance output in Physical Education subject.

According to Reese (2011), learning by doing is different from learning by watching others perform, reading others' instructions or descriptions, or listening to others' instructions or lectures since learning by doing refers to experiences that come directly from one's own activities. In spite of the fact that watching, reading, and listening are actions, they are not the types of actions that are considered to be learning by doing since they give the learner direct experience with actions that are described or demonstrated rather than with actions, they themselves undertake.

The Significant Difference in the Mean Gain Test Results between the Control Group and Experimental Group

Table 8 shows the significant difference in the mean gain test results between the control group and experimental group.

Table 8. *The Significant Difference in the Mean Gain Test Results Between the Control Group and Experimental Group*

Group	N	Mean	SD	Mean diff	df	t	Pvalue	Interpretation
Control	30	0.45	0.37					
Experimental	30	1.16	0.35	0.71	58	7.6	<0.00001	Significant

Table 8 presents the significant difference in the mean gain test results in the post-test results between the control group and experimental group results. Since $t(58)=7.6$, $p<0.00001$, and pvalue is less than the set level of confidence at .05, I conclude that there is a significant difference in the mean gain results between the control group ($M=0.45, SD=0.37$) and experimental group ($M=1.16, SD=0.35$). The result of the experimental group is significantly higher than the control group.

The outcome suggests that there is a significant difference between the experimental and control groups. Ho (2021) provided evidence in support of the premise that learning by doing can help students understand a subject better by having them carry out the task. Additionally, active participation fosters deeper learning and teaches students that making mistakes is acceptable since they can learn from them. Experiential learning is the new name for this methodology that was inspired by this mindset.

The evaluation of the SambaFest Dancercise video highlighted its exceptional quality across various dimensions: content, relevance, acceptability, and instructional aspects. Tables 1 to 4 consistently reported high mean scores, predominantly in the "Outstanding" range, indicating that the video aligns well with K-12 curriculum goals, provides effective learning objectives, and offers appropriate, easy-to-follow instructional materials. These findings resonate with literature emphasizing the importance of instructional quality in enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes (Kelly, 2019).

The SambaFest Dancercise video not only met the minimum standards but also exceeded expectations in terms of its cultural sensitivity and ability to stimulate learners' interest. This aligns with educational theories advocating for instructional materials that cater to diverse learner needs and foster active participation (Basic Education Competency in K-12 in The Philippines, 2012).

The study's results regarding learner performance in dance skills further underscore the effectiveness of the SambaFest Dancercise video. Tables 5 to 8 demonstrated significant improvements in the experimental group compared to the control group in both post-test scores and mean gain test results. Specifically, the experimental group showed a notable increase in their dance performance, supported by substantial statistical differences (Ho, 2021).

The significant difference in post-test results between the control and experimental groups (Table 7) indicates that the use of the

SambaFest Dancercise video positively influenced students' dance skills. This finding corroborates previous research highlighting the benefits of active learning methodologies, such as learning-by-doing, which are central to the experiential learning approach promoted in this study (Reese, 2011).

The outcomes of this study have significant implications for PE instruction and curriculum development. By integrating innovative instructional tools like the SambaFest Dancercise video, educators can enhance student engagement and learning outcomes. The video's ability to cater to diverse learning styles and cultural backgrounds promotes inclusive education practices, aligning with contemporary educational standards (Kelly, 2019).

Furthermore, the study underscores the importance of continuous improvement in educational materials and practices. Suggestions for further enhancing the video's content and instructional features, as highlighted in the recommendations, aim to optimize its effectiveness and applicability across different educational settings (Ho, 2021).

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study has demonstrated the significant impact of the SambaFest Dancercise video on both instructional quality and learner performance in Physical Education (PE). The evaluation of the video across various dimensions—content, relevance, acceptability, and instructional aspects—consistently revealed outstanding ratings, indicating its alignment with educational goals and its effectiveness in engaging students.

One of the key insights from this study is the importance of integrating culturally sensitive and engaging instructional materials in PE. The SambaFest Dancercise video not only met educational standards but also exceeded expectations by fostering active participation and catering to diverse learner needs. This underscores the value of incorporating instructional tools that resonate with students' cultural backgrounds and interests, thereby enhancing their learning experiences (Basic Education Competency in K–12 in The Philippines, 2012).

Moreover, the study's findings on learner performance highlight the effectiveness of experiential learning approaches, such as learning-by-doing. The significant improvements observed in the experimental group compared to the control group underscore the video's ability to enhance students' dance skills and overall performance in PE. Educators can leverage these findings by adopting similar active learning strategies that promote hands-on experiences and deeper engagement among students (Reese, 2011).

Viewed from the findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher recommends the following:

Encourage educators to integrate experiential learning approaches in PE instruction through active participation and practical application, exemplified by the SambaFest Dancercise video. Provide opportunities for continuous professional development focused on instructional design and multimedia utilization. This dual approach empowers educators to effectively utilize tools like the SambaFest Dancercise video, optimizing student learning outcomes by fostering a hands-on learning environment that enhances understanding and mastery of physical activities.

Collaborate with curriculum developers to formally integrate the culturally relevant and engaging SambaFest Dancercise video into the PE curriculum of Kapingkong National High School. Encourage the school administration to issue memoranda for its full implementation, aligning the integration with the learning competencies outlined in the K to 12 Curriculum. This proactive step ensures that instructional materials resonate with students' cultural backgrounds and interests, promoting inclusivity and catering to diverse learning needs.

Advocate for the adoption of the SambaFest Dancercise video in other schools within the Division of Sultan Kudarat and beyond. Encourage these schools to introduce and adopt the instructional tool in their PE programs, aiming to broaden its reach and impact across the division. Establish robust mechanisms for collecting feedback from educators and students on the video's effectiveness. Use this feedback to iteratively improve its content, delivery, and features, ensuring continuous enhancement of instructional quality and alignment with educational goals.

Support future research endeavors focused on enhancing the content and overall features of the SambaFest Dancercise video. Encourage studies that explore new methodologies, technologies, and approaches to further improve student engagement and learning outcomes in physical education settings. This research-driven approach promotes innovation in PE instruction, advancing educational practices and ensuring the continued effectiveness of instructional tools like the SambaFest Dancercise video.

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